

The role of coaching in supporting schools to adopt open schooling

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Abstract

This paper presents the idea that coaching can play a crucial role in facilitating the adoption of open schooling by educational institutions and investigates the methods through which it can achieve this. The typical difficulties of open education are discussed, and a brief comparison is made between coaching and other similar interventions like psychotherapy, teaching, mentoring, and training. The paper adopts the perspective of a teacher transitioning into a life coach and delves into the advantages of coaching for both students and educators as they embrace the principles of open schooling. The paper encompasses a range of strategies by which coaching can support educators within the framework of open schooling. Furthermore, it examines how coaching can aid students in putting open schooling principles into practice. In summary, the paper underscores the pivotal role that coaching plays in facilitating the successful implementation of open schooling, helping teachers and students get the most out of it.

Key words: open schooling, open schooling challenges, coaching, educational coaching

Introduction

While there is quite a lot of information on coaching in education in the literature, I have found little specific data on the combination of coaching and open schooling, but I strongly believe that bringing them together would enhance the quality of the educational process.

Open schooling promotes a flexible and inclusive learning environment that encourages students to explore the world through science, an approach to education where students identify real-life problems that they CARE about, want to KNOW and DO actions as to find out solutions collaborating with their communities and science professionals. (CONNECT project n. d.)

Coaching is defined by the European Mentoring and Coaching Council as “supporting clients in achieving greater self-awareness, improved self-management skills and increased self-efficacy, so they develop their own goals and solutions appropriate to their context”. (Robins 2017, p. 121) As the ICF states, “The process of coaching often unlocks previously untapped sources of imagination, productivity and leadership”. (ICF, n.d.) Elaine Cox, senior lecturer within the International Centre for Coaching and Mentoring Studies at Oxford Brookes University, defines coaching as a “facilitated, dialogic learning process”. (Bennett and Campone, 2017)

In fact, the term “coaching” appeared in the education area in the 1830s at Oxford University, where a student support activity was initiated for students to take the exams. (Stănciulescu, 2021) Thereafter, academic coaching principles were borrowed in performance sports, then performance business (Roshia 2014, p. 119; Stănciulescu, 2021) and nowadays coaching is used in various fields (Pürçek, 2014, p. 1), including education, where the popularity of coaching is on the rise.

Coaching is a future-oriented intervention that can serve as a valuable tool, providing support to schools in adopting open schooling and addressing the challenges that it faces, benefiting teachers, students, and communities, and ensuring a better future for this approach of education.

This paper can help teachers and school leaders consider coaching in open schooling implementation for an easier and more successful implementation.

Coaching and other professions

Coaching, as previously understood, is a distinct intervention from similar others like teaching, mentoring, training, counselling or psychotherapy. As Rosha (2014) states, “Each intervention has its own purpose and is delivered by experts with different qualifications and different relationships with the individual.” All these interventions can be helpful in different educational contexts, used separately or combined.

Because sometimes the word “coaching” is used for mentoring, teaching (van Nieuwerburgh, 2016, p. 1) or training, generating confusion, I will briefly address the differences between coaching and other similar interventions, especially those related to the educational field such as teaching, and mentoring. Coaching shares some similarities with the professions aforementioned, but it has its specific key features.

First of all, coaching is addressed to people who are mentally healthy and have no psychological issues, being distinct in this regard of psychotherapy.

In my opinion, the most appropriate definition for coaching in the educational context is this one proposed by the International Centre for Coaching in Education (ICCE): “A one-to-one conversation focused on the enhancement of learning and development through increasing self-awareness and a sense of personal responsibility where the coach facilitates the self-directed learning of the coachee through questioning, active listening and appropriate challenge in a supportive and encouraging climate.” (coachingskills.umn.edu, n.d.) with the mention that coaching conversation could also be a group conversation.

Some differences between classical teaching and coaching are: teaching usually takes place in a formal setting, in a classroom of a school. Coaching usually takes place in a neutral space for both client and coach, and coaching has been taking place more and more online recently.

In teaching, a school curriculum defines the content and skills that students should acquire, coaching involves the beneficiary selecting the theme they want to work on and the results they wish for. The teacher is required to be an expert in the field they teach, while in coaching, the coach is not required to be an expert in the client's field.

The purpose of coaching is to assist individuals in learning, not to teach them. (Whitemore, 2017, p. 13) Different forms of grades and exams are used to evaluate the learning process and student results in teaching, but coaching does not involve grades or exams. In teaching, homework is given to students, but in coaching, beneficiaries are not given homework; to achieve better results, they are encouraged to take responsibility for their own actions. (van Nieuwerburgh and Barr, 2016.) Often, in teaching, students have a passive role in receiving the information taught (Rosha, 2014), while the beneficiary has an active role in the coaching process.

Mentoring in education refers to “a series of one-to-one conversations in which a more experienced person asks questions, provides guidance, shares knowledge, and gives advice to support a learner to improve their performance and achieve success within a nurturing relationship. In addition to being experienced in the area of interest, the mentor should be effective at building relationships and skilled at supporting others to learn.” (van Nieuwerburgh and Barr, 2016) Unlike a mentor, the coach does not necessarily have expertise in the student's field. Other characteristics of mentoring, such as giving advice and providing role models (Rosha, 2014, p. 124) are not found in coaching. Unlike mentoring, which often involves experts providing specific advice or solutions, coaches do not offer solutions or suggestions.

Open schooling challenges

Open schooling aims to bring together diverse sectors (educational, social, enterprise, and cultural) in order to improve the quality of learning for learners (Ramirez-Montoya, 2020) and to equip students with the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values they need to thrive in the 21st century. (CONNECT International Conference on Open Schooling #CICOS2023, n. d.) In this endeavor open schooling faces many challenges. Some of them are the capacity to bring together schools, local communities, and enterprise for collaboration, lack of access to the internet and technology for many communities (Ramirez-Montoya, 2020), the busy curriculum, and the many duties that teachers need to accomplish on a daily basis. Another obstacle in the open schooling implementation refers to the costs involved by open schooling activities, such as the costs of materials used in educational activities or the costs for transporting children to different locations where learning activities take place. On top of that, teachers must take on greater responsibility to supervise students during off-school activities.

Other challenges are the difficulty of accessing resources in a non-native language or finding suitable materials in teachers and students' native language, parents' lack of time to participate in activities with their children, and finding community representatives for collaboration.

A list of challenges refers to "teachers" professional difficulties in implementing this innovative approach to education. In open schooling teachers need to implement or create activities that are different from the curriculum ones, they need to use knowledge that is not used in regular classes and approaches that are different from teaching as lecturing. (Poeck et al., 2022)

In the context of open schooling, coaching can be provided to teachers and students, and I will start with teachers because "teachers' practices in the classroom are the greatest predictor of student achievement", as Knight and Bush state. (Devine, Meyers and Houssemand, 2013, p. 382)

How can teachers benefit from coaching in embracing open schooling?

As we have seen, the implementation of open schooling can be very challenging for teachers, but fortunately, some of the teachers' difficulties in the open schooling context can be addressed by coaching. First of all, open schooling challenges teachers to change and learn, and coaching is a powerful tool in this respect. (Devine, 2013) As Lofthouse (2018) claims, "Coaching has been evolving as a form of professional development for teachers and school leaders for several decades, and now exists in many forms." These forms of coaching can be used in an open schooling context assisting teachers to successfully put into practice this approach to education. Evidence indicates that some coaching approaches were already successfully utilized with teachers. (Devine, Meyers, and Houssemand, 2013, p. 1383)

Coaching can help teachers find the necessary time to implement open schooling activities in all the many tasks they have to perform, provide emotional support, and at the same time reduce the negative effects of educational performance (Lofthouse, 2018) diminishing stress and enhancing work and well-being. (Grant, Green, and Rynsaardt, 2010)

Even if it doesn't provide solutions, coaching is a powerful tool for educators to find their own solutions to open schooling obstacles. A great advantage of coaching is that it allows teachers to reflect on their own actions, a very important competence in the world of speed in which we live and in which no one has time.

A coach can aid teachers in understanding the ways in which they require improved skills and embracing innovative teaching approaches. The first beneficiaries of coaching used with teachers will be students, as teachers' coaching can enhance student attainment. (Lofthouse, 2018, p. 11).

Coaching used with teachers can be either individual or group coaching.

How can students benefit from coaching in the context of open schooling?

The 21st century brought its own challenges with it (Devine, Meyers and Houssemand 2013, p. 1382), so the open schooling approach aims to expand the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values that students need to succeed in this century (CONNECT International Conference on Open Schooling #CICOS2023, n.d.), and coaching has the potential to be very beneficial in this endeavor. There is already evidence to support the use of coaching as a tool for student learning and development. (Devine et al., 2013, p.1382)

There is also evidence to support that coaching positively influences the "beneficiaries" ability to access the necessary and efficient cognitive processes and metacognitive skills to meet the challenges of the school environment (Brevik Saethern et al. 2022, p.349), skills so necessary in open schooling settings.

Developing the ability of self-directing learning is a priority for students in open schooling, this being the first step in learning to learn. (Li-ya, 2003) Because in the coaching process they do not feel judged and evaluated, students are more open to the learning process and more available to look for solutions to the challenges they face in self-directed learning.

Research shows that there are many students who believe that science is not for them, and these students lack "science capital", especially those from disadvantaged groups. (CONNECT International Conference on Open Schooling #CICOS2023 n.d.) This is where coaching comes in helping students to gradually shift from a fixed mindset to a growth mindset.

In secondary schools students are already under stress (Green et al., 2007; Roussis & Wells, 2008) and coaching can help them manage the stress (Devine et al.,2013 p.1386) that can be added by open schooling activities in order for them to enjoy those activities and make the most of them. Working with a coach, students can better manage their emotions, which facilitates learning because learning is dependent on emotional state. (Jim Kwik, n.d.)

Students can be helped by a coach to overcome open schooling challenges, boost their efficiency and motivation. (Brevik Saethern et al. 2022) A coach has the patience to work with a child or teenager, which a teacher may not have in certain situations.

Coaching can help students learn for themselves, not just for exams and grades, which classical teaching tends to fail. (van Nieuwerburgh and Barr, 2016, p.1). Coaching with students can be done individually or in a group.

Conclusions

Coaching is an intervention that has already been successfully used in education for both teachers and students. In the context of this paper, coaching is distinct from other similar interventions like psychotherapy, teaching, mentoring, or training, and it is important to be aware of these differences in order to understand which of them, alone or combined, is better to be chosen in order to enhance the quality of education in the 21st century.

Because it addresses some of the difficulties that open schooling faces, coaching can be very helpful in putting open schooling into practice for both teachers and students in a variety of

ways. Combining coaching and open schooling can enhance the educational process, but further research is required to gather more evidence-based knowledge about how coaching can support open schooling.

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